

Role of newspapers in English

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Abstract

Newspapers have been the most conventional and popular medium of conveying local, regional, national and international news to the readers. Newspaper serve us the latest happenings in different parts of the world through a network of correspondents and news agencies. The national dailies employ their correspondents and reporters in all the major cities of the world. The major newspapers like the New York Times, The Pravda, The Sunday Mail, The Times of India & The Hindustan Times would, shape and influence the views, opinions and attitudes of millions of readers throughout the world. The media is best defined by the roles they play in society. They educate, inform and entertain through news, features and analysis in the press. They also produce documentaries, dramas, current affairs programmes, public service announcements, magazine programmes and other forms of programming for radio and television. The media is a conduit through which voices, perspectives and lives are brought into the public sphere. In the last decade, Africa has witnessed a massive growth of on-line media, which is being exploited by both urban and rural communities to access and deliver information for social and business purposes.

Key words: Superiority, advancement, vision, definition, realization, attitude, correspondence, major, different, education, sensation

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Отрывок

Газеты были наиболее традиционным и популярным средством передачи читателям местных, региональных, национальных и международных новостей. Газеты сообщают нам о последних событиях в разных частях мира через сеть корреспондентов и информационных агентств. Национальные

ежедневные газеты нанимают своих корреспондентов и репортеров во всех крупных городах мира. Крупнейшие газеты, такие как «Нью-Йорк таймс», «Правда», «Санди мейл», «Таймс оф Индия» и «Хиндустан таймс», будут формировать и влиять на взгляды, мнения и отношения миллионов читателей во всем мире. Средства массовой информации лучше всего определяются ролями, которые они играют в обществе. Они обучают, информируют и развлекают посредством новостей, статей и анализа в прессе. Они также производят документальные фильмы, драмы, программы о текущих событиях, социальную рекламу, журнальные программы и другие формы программ для радио и телевидения. Средства массовой информации являются каналом, через который голоса, точки зрения и жизнь передаются в общественную сферу. За последнее десятилетие в Африке произошел массовый рост онлайн-СМИ, которые используются как городскими, так и сельскими сообществами для доступа и доставки информации в социальных и деловых целях.

Ключевые слова: Превосходство, продвижение, видение, определение, реализация, отношение, соответствие, главное, разное, образование, ощущение.

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Ko'chirma

Gazetalar mahalliy, mintaqaviy, milliy va xalqaro yangiliklarni o'quvchilarga etkazishning eng an'anaviy va ommabop vositasi bo'lib kelgan. Gazetalar muxbirlar va axborot agentliklari tarmog'i orqali dunyoning turli burchaklarida sodir bo'layotgan so'nggi voqealar haqida bizga xabar beradi. Milliy gazetalar o'z muxbirlari va muxbirlarini dunyoning barcha yirik shaharlarida ishlaydi. New York Times, Pravda, Sunday Mail, Times of India va Hindustan Times kabi yirik gazetalar

butun dunyo bo'ylab millionlab o'quvchilarning qarashlari, qarashlari va munosabatlarini shakllantiradi va ta'sir qiladi. Ommaviy axborot vositalari jamiyatda o'ynaydigan rollari bilan eng yaxshi ta'riflanadi. Ular yangiliklar, xususiyatlar va matbuot tahlillari orqali ta'lim beradi, xabardor qiladi va ko'ngil ochadi. Shuningdek, ular hujjatli filmlar, dramalar, dolzarb voqealar dasturlari, jamoatchilik e'lonlari, jurnal dasturlari va radio va teledasturlarning boshqa shakllarini ishlab chiqaradilar. Ommaviy axborot vositalari - bu ovozlari, qarashlar va hayotni jamoatchilikka etkazish kanalidir. So'nggi o'n yil ichida Afrikada shahar va qishloq jamoalari ijtimoiy va biznes maqsadlarida ma'lumotlarga kirish va etkazib berish uchun foydalaniladigan onlayn ommaviy axborot vositalarining katta o'sishi kuzatildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Zo'rlik, ko'tarilish, ko'rish, ta'rif, amalga oshirish, munosabat, muvofiqlik, asosiy, har xil, ta'lim, his qilish.

Newspapers can be divided into three basic types: dailies, weeklies and special interest newspapers . In addition , almost all newspapers have their own online edition which provides news on the Internet.

Daily newspapers print world, national and local news. Many of them also have a section about events that happen in the area in which the reader lives. Most dailies are distributed in the morning, but in some large cities newspapers have an afternoon or evening edition that comes out when people travel home from work.

Sunday newspapers have additional features and more pages than weekday editions. Topics like entertainment, finance or travel are included in separate sections, which sometimes make Sunday papers so large that they are difficult to handle.

Weekly papers are distributed in a much smaller area and have news that is more local and personal. In small communities people know each other and are often interested in activities of their friends and neighbours.

Special interest papers are newspapers for a special part of the population, like Hispanics in America. Some of them also focus on certain topics like sports or business. Newspapers are publications usually issued daily, weekly, or at other regular

times that provide news, views, features, and other information of public

interest and that often carry advertising. Although newspapers traditionally

have been produced as print publications (generally they are printed on coarse, low-cost paper known as newsprint), the newspaper concept today is changing rapidly. While there are still more than 11,000 daily newspapers in the world—including more than 1,400 paid-for dailies in the United States—many of those newspapers are also published online, and there are a growing number of “newspapers” that appear online exclusively

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